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STUDY OF BIO GAS PRODUCTION FROM WASTES “COW DUNG & POULTRY WASTE”

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ABSTRACT

In India, the population of people is increasing who prefer chicken meat as a protein source. The population of India is 1.27 billion in 2014. The poultry meat production is estimated to be 2.19 million metric tonnes as per 2010-11 estimates. India's annual per-capita consumption of chicken meat is estimated around 2.2kg. As a result more chicken meat is required to be produced. In Jaipur daily consumption of chicken meat is in range of between 3000 to 3500 kg. During processing of chicken meat, some quantity of waste is produced.

The major problem is how to dispose this bio waste from slaughter houses. In this research we discuss about disposing and production of energy in the form of biogas from waste material. The production of biogas is completed by anaerobic digestion. This will help to enhance the production of energy along with disposal problem of chicken waste (CW).

Here, we discuss about a developed prototype digester tank. The capacity of this digester is 20 liters and made of Poly Ethylene Terephthalate. We used this digester tank for fermentation of cow dung and chicken waste to generate Bio-gas. Starch powder is added in to the digester as additive to maintain ph level.

KEY WORDS: Cow Dung (CD), Chicken Meat (CM), Chicken Waste (CW), Bio-gas, Digester Tank, Anaerobic Digestion (AD), Starch Powder (SP).

INTRODUCTION:-

In India, there is a large quantity of chicken waste produced. The poultry industry is growing day by day concentrated within the urban as well as rural community. The aim of this paper is to show that the chicken waste can be used as the feeding material to produce biogas [1].

Energy is generally classified in either renewable or non-renewable. Bio gas comes in the category of renewable energy sources. Renewable energy is energy generated from natural resources and can be replenished within a short period of time. Some renewable energy sources include biomass, water (hydro-power), geothermal, wind, and solar [2].

Global depletion of energy supply due to the continuing over-utilization is being a major problem of the present and future world community. Today's lifestyle is energy demanding, so we need exploring and exploiting new sources of energy which are renewable as well as eco-friendly. Biogas technology provides a very attractive route to utilize certain categories of biomass for meeting partial energy needs. Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a technology widely used for treatment of organic/biological waste for biogas production and provides a source of energy while simultaneously resolving ecological and agrochemical issues. The anaerobic fermentation of manure for biogas production does not reduce its value as a fertilizer supplement, as available nitrogen and other substances remain in the treated sludge [3].

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a natural biological decomposition of organic material in a controlled environment in the absence of oxygen. In this deoxidized- zone, bacteria are employed to decompose the proteinaceous and carbonaceous materials producing biogas and sludge.

Depending on the type of raw material, biogas contains on average 50-70% methane, 30-40% carbon dioxide, 1-2% nitrogen, 5-10% hydrogen, and trace amounts of hydrogen sulfide and water vapor [4].

One of the burning problems facing the world today is the management of all sources which endangers the existence of human life. The present study aims at producing biogas from chicken droppings and to utilize the residual sludge as bio fertilizer. Biogas production is a complex biochemical reaction found to take place under the action of delicately pH sensitive microbes mainly bacteria in the presence of little or no oxygen. Three major groups of bacteria (Hydrolytic, Acidogenesis, Acetogenesis and Methanogenesis) are responsible for breaking down the complex polymers in biomass waste to form biogas at anaerobic conditions.

Biogas production is slightly slow at the beginning and the end period of observation. This is predicted because biogas production rate in batch condition is directly proportional to specific growth rate of methanogenic bacteria in the bio digester [5] [6].

A gas produced by the breakdown of organic matter through Anaerobic Digestion (AD). It is one of the renewable energy sources, like solar and wind energy. There are many characteristics that makes different from another sources of renewal energy such as this is 20% lighter than air, ignition temperature is in range of 650 to 750 0C, odorless & color less gas with blue flame, having 20 mega joules (MJ) / m³ caloric value, 60% efficient to burn in conventional biogas stove [7].

Biogas is a well-established fuel that can supplement or even replace wood as an energy source for cooking and lighting in developing countries. Currently, as the fossil-based fuels become scarce and more expensive, the economics of biogas production is turning out to be more favorable. Biogas is a readily available energy resource that significantly reduces greenhouse-gas emission compared to the emission of landfill gas to the atmosphere [8].

Biogas plants can help in the fight against global warming by allowing to burn methane from organic waste of the poultry farm, instead of letting it escape into the atmosphere where it adds to the greenhouse effect [9].

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS :-

Chicken waste is collected from chicken house, Malviya Nagar, Jaipur. Cow dung is collected from Jagatpura. Starch powder is added as additive.

After collecting CW, it is grinded in grinding machine to decrease particle size decreases and to increase surface area.

Fig-1: Grinded Chicken Waste

Fig-2: - Feeding Material of Digester (CD, CW, WATER, SP)

Method

First of all we will prepare the experimental setup which includes a digester tank of 20 liter capacity, Poly Ethylene Terephthalate rubber tube for storing bio-gas, gas pipe to connect digester tank and rubber tube, T-valve, and gas valve.

Fig-3: Digester plant for Bio gas production.

Where:-

- A= Digester tank made by Poly Ethylene Terephthalate. (20L)
- B= Gas pipe for receive gas.
- C= T-valve
- D= Cylindrical Gas collection tank (Butyl Rubber tube)
- E= Gas valve (nozzle) for burning gas.

Since the digester bottle is transparent so we paint the digester bottle with black color. Because, in the presence of light algae is produced and algae causes the production of oxygen. Anaerobic reaction is work out in the absence of oxygen so we paint the digester tank. After that gas pipe is connected to digester tank and t-valve and this T-valve is connected to rubber tube and gas valve. Gas valve is used to burn bio-gas.

Now, for preparing feeding material, we take 3kg of chicken waste and grind it in mixing machine so that the particle size is decreased. After that we take 10 liter water in a bucket and 500gm starch powder is mixed in it and 5.5kg of fresh cow dung and 3kg of chicken waste is mixed in 10liter water. Thus a paste is prepared as feeding material for the digester tank. This material is poured in digester tank with the help of funnel. And this digester tank is made air tight with the help of super glue.

Fig-4: - Quantity of feeding material for Digester tank.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

We hold this experimental setup for 30 days. At the end of 30 days the gas collection tube filled with gas completely. In the beginning 3 days, there was no gas produced in the digester. After 3 days yielding of gas was started. After 15 days yielding of gas is speedily. The production of gas was at peak level between 25th to 30th days.

After 30 days we checked by burning the gas, the gas did not burn properly in starting because carbon dioxide was present in the gas and then we passed this gas through “Potassium Hydroxide solution” (KOH) with 5% concentration. This KOH solution absorbed CO₂ gas. After passing gas, it started to burn with flame.

We can obtain a good quality of bio-gas by controlling pH level of feeding material.

Bio-gas with good quality will burn with blue flame without passing through the KOH solution.

Table - 1 Detail of Parameters Calculated for Inlet and Outlet Slurry

S. Nos	Parameter	PH	TOTAL SOLID	NOS VOLATILE SOLID	VOLATILE SOLID
01	Inlet substrate	6.5	70.19 %	17.5%	82.5%
02	Outlet products	6.0	27.96 %	14.89%	85.11

Figure -5: Inlet & Outlet pH of Material

This graph shows the pH level of the feeding material. It is measured by pH meter. The pH level of the inlet material is 6.5 and outlet material is 6.0.

Figure 6: Total Solid of Inlet & Outlet Material

This graph shows the quantity of total solid present in the feeding material of digester. Total solids are the measure of all the suspended and dissolved solids. The quantity of total solid in inlet material is 70.19% and 27.96% in outlet slurry.

Figure 7: Volatile Solid of Inlet & Outlet Material

This graph shows the quantity of the volatile solid present in the feeding material. Volatile solids are the solids that are lost on ignition of the material. The quantity of the volatile solid present in the inlet material is 82.5% and 85.11% in outlet slurry.

Figure 8: Non-Volatile Solid of Material

This graph shows the quantity of non volatile solid present in the feeding material. Non volatile solids are the solids that remain after burning of material at 750° C in muffle oven. The quantity of non volatile solid present in the inlet material is 17.5% and 14.89% in outlet slurry.

Table - 2 Observations of the Experiment

S. No.	Time Duration	Sample appearance	Evolution of gas	Ignition of Gas	Odour	Bio-Gas produced (m ³)	Cumulative Bio Gas (m ³)
1	Day 1	No gas produced				0	0
2	Day 5	Biogas is produced in very small quantity	Temperature of Digester is increasing		Smell is like CNG	0.042	0.042
3	Day 10	Biogas is produced small quantity	Temperature of Digester is increasing	Gas is burning with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.044	0.086
4	Day 15	Biogas is produced in good quantity	Temperature of Digester is increasing	Gas is burning with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.064	0.15
5	Day 20	Biogas is produced and gas collection is almost full	Temperature of Digester is increasing	Gas is burning with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.074	0.224
6	Day 25	Biogas is produced and gas collection tank is full	Temperature of Digester is increasing	Gas is burning with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.086	0.31
7	Day 30	Biogas is produced and gas collection is almost full	Temperature of Digester is increasing	Gas is burning with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.061	0.371

The following graph shows the production of bio-gas graphically.

Fig- 9: - Quantity of Bio Gas

The above graph shows the production rate of bio gas. Initially there is no gas production in digester. The yield of bio gas is started in the middle of first week, and this production of bio gas is at peak level in the fourth week.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE OF WORK

As we produced bio-gas by biological waste, the main objective of this research work is to manage the biological wastage from slaughter house and poultry farms. Instead of disposing these waste materials, we can produce energy in the form of flammable gas. This gaseous energy is the renewable source of energy. And also this method has a very low cost. Initially, this method seems costly but later this method is a very low cost energy production. Hence bio-gas production is a cheap method to produce energy.

In the future, this method of generation of energy can be substitute of non renewable sources of energy. By this method we obtain bio-gas as well as fertilizer. This type of fertilizer is improved and very useful for crops. Crops will grow up by using this fertilizer. We must use this method at a large scale so that consumption of the natural energy sources can be decrease. This project of generation of bio gas is also environment friendly. In India, soil fertility status is decreasing day by day. Bio gas plant also helps to improve the fertility of soil.

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